

STUDY OF THE SEDATIVE EFFECT OF A DRY EXTRACT BASED ON LOCAL MEDICINAL PEONY (*PAEONIA OFFICINALIS* L.)

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Introduction In order to create medicinal preparations based on local plant raw materials and introduce them into medical practice, it is necessary to study the specific activity of the developed medicinal preparations. A dry extract with a calming effect was obtained from local raw materials using the polyextraction method. roots and rhizomes of the medicinal peony (*Paeonia officinalis* L.).

The aim of the study is to determine the specific activity of dry extract based on local raw materials. peony (*Paeonia officinalis* L.)

Materials and methods The sedative effect of dry extract of peony (*Paeonia officinalis* L.) was studied using two methods: by determining its effect on motor activity and by the ability to prolong urethane anesthesia.

The experiment was conducted on white mice weighing 20-23g. White mice from the experimental and control groups were placed in a chamber suspended on a kymograph 30 minutes after the administration of the drug, and the motor activity of the white mice was recorded for 30 minutes.

Sedative effect dry extract of peony (*Paeonia officinalis* L.) was studied using a modified method of prolonging the hypnotic effect of urethane. The experiment was carried out on white rats weighing 180–210 g.

Artificial sleep was induced by intravenous administration of a 1% aqueous solution of urethane. Urethane has a depressant effect on the central nervous system, reducing brain activity and causing a state similar to sleep. The drugs were administered 30 minutes before urethane. The ability of the drug to prolong the effect of urethane was assessed, for which the time of falling asleep (the moment of loss of the reflex of turning over) and the duration of the lateral position (sleep) were recorded for each animal. The third group served as a control; the time of falling asleep and the duration of urethane sleep were recorded for these animals.

The obtained data were statistically processed using the STATISTICA program using the paired Student's t-test.

Results and discussions When studying the effect of dry extract of peony (*Paeonia officinalis* L.) on motor activity, it was found that with a single intragastric administration of an aqueous solution of dry extract at a dose of 250 mg / kg, mice showed lethargy and low mobility, a decrease in the number of orientation reflexes compared to the control. In rats receiving dry extract of medicinal peony at a dose of 250 mg / kg, a significant decrease in the latency of falling asleep to 1.7 ± 0.2 minutes was observed, indicating a rapid onset of a sedative effect ($p < 0.05$ compared to the control). In addition, the duration of sleep in this group increased more than 2 times compared to the control and was 195.2 ± 15.3 minutes ($p < 0.05$).

Thus, the results of the experiment demonstrate a pronounced potentiating effect of the dry extract of peony on urethane sleep. The extract significantly accelerates the onset of sleep and

increases its duration, which indicates the presence of a sedative effect. These data confirm the possibility of using the dry extract of peony as a means for correcting sleep disorders and anxiety states.

Conclusions The drug under study is a dry extract from local peony (*Paeonia officinalis*L.), has a reliable sedative effect.